

The Compression of Information

Information about this document

Author: Ing. Jan Lochman
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7839051
File name: the-com-of-infor.pdf
File type: pdf (Portable Document Format)
Keywords: text size, text structure, information, compression, decompression
Language: English
License: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Pages: 3
Published: February 22, 2023
Size: 37 kB
Title: The Compression of Information
Updated: April 18, 2023
Version: 2

In what sense?

The idea of information sharing is related to the idea of making notes/excerpts while studying. For example, some students have a lot of time to prepare exam questions, that is, create new compressed documents from lectures, notes, scripts, or other sources (both full-size and compressed sources). So they commit either compression, if the original source is full size, or information restructuring, or both. And those who have time, then continue with further compression, making other, more concise extracts from the worked-out questions, which they can use as a guide or just study material.

Known levels of abstraction and visualization methods

In this text, therefore, compression is understood as a form of shortening done by a person, however, it turns out that AI models such as chatbots (e.g. chat GPT 3) can already handle it. It is certain that the form of abridgment could be drawn on a scale and everyone will have it somehow different, but we already know certain generally defined forms of abridgment. This is, for example, a lecture or a seminar, where some broader work should be presented in a concise form (e.g. a script or a certain virtual knowledge of a certain subject), and further, for example, extracts or notes, which de facto also summarize what was said or written. The draw is then a kind of third level of abridgment.

Abbreviation does not have to be done only by writing and rewriting, for example, highlighting parts of the text in color in a textbook is also a form of compressing information into a certain distinct idea, for example in a paragraph. In a similar way, highlighting works in notes, that is, a compressed document of the second order, on the third.

The benefit of information technology

And what does new media bring? Laptops only bring a different form of compression. Instead of manual writing, we write digitally. This certainly has advantages in facilitating, for example, information retrieval (or a certain data mining in notes), but it can have negative effects on learning abilities since research shows that memorization occurs mainly in a process where the student has to make some effort. If everything is simple and without effort, or if it is complicated by, for example, the need to master technology, then the result of the effectiveness of the study decreases (a similar principle applied to older students in the case of processing term papers on Wikipedia, where they rather learned to work with sources, text and the online editor, rather than would immerse themselves in the knowledge of the text itself).

Technology today also allows us to take audio or video recordings. Here, however, we cannot speak of abridgment, but rather of copying a rearrangement of, for example, a lecture. If videos allowed for easy editing, for example drawing in screencasting, or inserting certain VR objects, we could talk about a certain type of audiovisual shortening. So far, there are just PDF drawing tools in, for example, the Microsoft Edge browser (which apparently works only on Windows operation system as of March 2023). In the future, however, digitization will have rather only advantages – it is already clear today that long notes/excerpts in digital form enable faster search for ideas – however, this development is hampered, by the slow development of tools for working with text (we work with text digitally in the same way for the last 50 years or longer).

Resource types are something to think about

The principle of abbreviation is actually also encountered in the types of sources: secondary – tertiary – (quarterly). It is interesting that the transition from primary to secondary is not a shortening, but rather an expansion. A few short studies are translated from scientific to non-scientific language and it is formed in a kind of descriptive form, so the amount of text increases. On the contrary, when compiling a tertiary source (e.g. encyclopedia) from sources of popular science, compression has traditionally occurred, but in a sense Wikipedia has broken this, when information can be compiled in a 1:1 ratio or even information on a topic can be expanded. However, the general idea of an encyclopedia is that it is a compressed information of human knowledge, so it should be called an abridgment. And what are quarterly resources? It could be the data, but since we don't understand the data, should it be the metadata of the data, or perhaps some simplifications in the form of images created by analyzing and displaying data from certain sources? The problem is that with data we are already getting out of the field that can be easily understood by humans.

How far can it be compressed?

De facto to zero, de facto to the point where information ceases to be information and ceases to have informative value for a person. For example, with students, information may lose value the moment they know the subject. Just say semantics and the student will imagine everything about semantics. The maximum compression of the information originally contained in a 200-page textbook or 72 hours of video can be one word. Even the word semantics itself has a certain meaning in the scientific discipline of semantics, so it is not just about compression for one particular person.

And the opposite of compression?

If it can be compressed, it should also be decompressed. But not for ordinary people equivalent decompressed document appears after compression. In the general understanding, however, the volume of data (text) about a certain subject should also increase exponentially. However, we should be thinking here about a certain form of maximum possible comprehensible expression. Because expression can either occur by adding additional knowledge of the field – here everything is probably in order and understanding depends on the structure of the information or its display, but also by adding ballast text, which optically increases the information, but creates incomprehensibility, or barrenness and difficulty of reading or studies. De facto, a certain structure or system is disturbed and chaos arises, or a more advanced structure with which any person can already have problems.